

IKKINCHI TARTIBLI DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALARNI

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Annotatsiya: bu maqolda chegraviy masaladan boshlang'ich shartli masalaga o'tish qaralgan.

Kalit so'zlar: chegaraviy masala, boshlang'ich shart, Nyuton-Rafson metodi, Ridder usuli.

Анотация: в данной статье рассматривается переход от краевой задачи к начальной условной задаче.

Ключевые слова: краевая задача, начальное условие, метод Ньютона-Рафсона, метод Риддера.

Abstract: this article considers the transition from the boundary value problem to the initial conditional problem.

Keywords: boundary value problem, initial condition, Newton-Raphson method, Ridder method.

The simplest two-point boundary value problem is a second-order differential equation with one condition specified at $x = a$ and another one at $x = b$. Here is an example of such a problem:

$$y'' = f(x, y, y'), \quad y(a) = \alpha, \quad y(b) = \beta$$

(1)

Let us now attempt to turn Eqs. (1) into the initial value problem

$$y'' = f(x, y, y'), \quad y(a) = \alpha, \quad y'(a) = u$$

(2)

The key to success is finding the correct value of u . This could be done by trial and error: Guess u and solve the initial value problem by marching from $x = a$ to $x = b$. If the solution agrees with the prescribed boundary condition $y(b) = \beta$, we are done; otherwise we have to adjust u and try again. Clearly, this procedure is very tedious. More systematic methods become available to us if we realize that the determination of u is a root-finding problem. Because the solution of the initial value problem depends on $x = b$, the computed value of $y(b)$ is a function of u ; that is $y(b) = \theta(u)$.

Hence u is a root of

$$r(u) = \theta(u) - \beta \tag{3}$$

where $r(u)$ is the boundary residual (the difference between the computed and specified boundary value at $x = b$). We reject the method of bisection because it

involves too many evaluations of $\theta(u)$. In the Newton-Raphson method we run into the problem of having to compute $\frac{d\theta}{du}$, which can be done but not easily. That leaves Ridder's algorithm as our method of choice [2]. Here is the procedure we use in solving nonlinear boundary value problems: Specify the starting values u_1 and u_2 that must bracket the root u of Eq. (3). Apply Ridder's method to solve Eq. (3) for u . Note that each iteration requires evaluation of $\theta(u)$ by solving the differential equation as an initial value problem [1]. Having determined the value of u , solve the differential equations once more and record the results. If the differential equation is linear, any root-finding method will need only one interpolation to determine u because Ridder's method uses three points (u_1 , u_2 , and u_3), it is wasteful compared with linear interpolation, which uses only two points (u_1 and u_2). Therefore, we replace Ridder's method with linear interpolation whenever the differential equation is linear.

EXAMPLE 1: Numerical integration of the initial value problem

$$y'' + 4y = 4x, \quad y(0) = 0, \quad y'(0) = 0$$

yielded $y'(2) = 1.65364$. Use this information to determine the value of $y'(0)$ that would result in $y'(2) = 0$.

Solution. We use linear interpolation

$$u = u_2 - \theta(u_2) \frac{u_2 - u_1}{\theta(u_2) - \theta(u_1)}$$

where in our case $u = y'(0)$ and $\theta(u) = y'(2)$. So far we are given $u_1 = 0$ and $\theta(u_1) = 1.65364$. To obtain the second point, we need another solution of the initial value problem. An obvious solution is $y = x$, which gives us $y(0) = 0$ and $y'(0) = y'(2) = 1$. Thus the second point is $u_2 = 1$ and $\theta(u_2) = 1$. Linear interpolation now yields

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati

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